

Benchmark of Accuracy and Precision of Generalized ("Microbiology v1.0.0") Microbiology Pipeline

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1 Abstract

This paper benchmarks Reshape Biotech’s Microbiology Pipeline (Microbiology v1.0.0), which integrates proprietary imaging techniques with machine learning analysis pipelines to digitally analyze microbiological plates. Automated colony counts were compared against human reference assessments across diverse sample types and conditions. The results show accuracy equivalent to human-human accuracy, high precision with minimal variability, and significant time savings in analysis. These findings demonstrate that the system reliably replicates human assessment while offering enhanced efficiency and traceability in microbiology workflows.

2 Introduction

Across a wide range of industries, microbiology plays a key role in either helping design and develop products or as something to be controlled, such as in product safety and shelf-life of products. Since the dawn of the field of microbiology, the most common way to quantify the presence, diversity, and concentration of microbes in samples has been based on the use of culture-based methods. Even today, 140 years after the invention of the petri dish, it remains a crucial tool, with many billions of petri dishes used yearly—often in manual workflows involving plate and sample preparation, inoculation, and subsequent analysis.

In this document, a characterization of the technology developed by Reshape Biotech (the legal entity “Reshape ApS”) is presented, documenting feasibility and result quality across a wide array of microbiological use cases.

More specifically:

- The ability of images produced by Reshape’s proprietary imaging technology to reproduce microbiological plates for digital analysis
- The ability of Reshape’s proprietary machine-learning-based analysis models to analyze samples
 - Evaluating accuracy and precision compared to human assessments

- Evaluating edge-case scenarios, categorized by either applications or various sample-induced complexities

We focus exclusively on verifying the performance of reading plates through imaging and automatic analysis. Because the underlying procedure (culture, incubation, etc.) does not change, these automated plate readers should not be considered an entirely different microbiological test method. Instead, we verify the ability to perform measurements equivalent to a trained human technician.

3 Methods

3.1 Nomenclature

”Analysis pipeline” is used in this document to describe an end to end processing of an image including several steps such as machine-learning based image segmentation and post-processing of various metrics to produce a final, high-level result (such as a count or classification of a plate).

”Imaging device” refers to the physical imaging device developed and manufactured by Reshape ApS which is used to generate the digital images used for analysis.

”CFU” refers to ”Colony forming unit”

”PDA” refers to ”Potato dextrose agar”

3.2 Defining Accuracy and Precision

Following ISO standard 5725-1 (ISO, 1994), the quality of measurement methods and results depends on both *accuracy* and *precision*:

- **Accuracy:** Closeness of agreement between a reference value for each sample (the average result from several trained human analysts) and the automatic assessment using a specific version of an analysis pipeline.
- **Precision:** Closeness of agreement between independent measurements, which can be quantified using the standard deviation of a series of measurements.

We use these definitions to evaluate the performance of the automatic solution.

3.3 Imaging Quality Verification

To ensure digital images can replace direct visual assessment, we employed two methods:

3.3.1 Equivalence Between Human Assessments on Images vs. Actual Plates

A set of petri dishes spanning environmental monitoring (with diverse morphologies) and dilution series of various reference samples was used to quantitatively confirm that the digital images accurately reproduced real-life samples as viewed by a technician.

3.3.2 Qualitative Review of Imaging Quality in Different Cases

All imaging devices are color-calibrated to show true color and morphology. Representative samples are shown in the results section, including mold colonies on potato dextrose agar (PDA), food samples on dichloran rose bengal chloramphenicol (DRBC) agar, and cream cheese inoculations on plate count agar (PCA). The imaging device enables resolution of colonies down to about 0.1 mm in diameter on a 90 mm plate and even smaller with optical zoom.

The automated analysis pipeline output can be reviewed directly by comparing annotations to observed plates.

(a) Raw epi-illumination image

(b) Annotated epi-illumination

Figure 1: Visual output used to manually review individual plates and understand analysis pipeline output.

3.4 Analysis Verification

To separate the ability of digital images to reproduce plates, all reference assessments are based on images rather than physical plates (see Section 2.2.1 for equivalence).

3.4.1 Sample Types

All samples are characterized by multiple dimensions, enabling performance evaluation for various use cases:

- Plate type: Surface inoculation vs. pour plate inoculation
- Density: Blank, low count (1–25 CFU, i.e. colony forming units), countable (25–300 CFU), TNTC (too numerous to count) if 300+ CFU

- Analysis type: TVC (total viable count)
- Organism type: Molds, yeast/bacterial
- Sample type: Environmental, water/membrane, product/sample/supernatant
- Artifacts: Bubbles, labels, barcodes

3.4.2 Accuracy of Automated Colony Counting

A dataset containing both reference human counts (assessed the same plates) and automatically generated counts was compiled. We then performed an *equivalence* analysis across these parameters, highlighting when automatic counts fell within acceptable bounds relative to the human reference.

The analysis of true and false results is based on being within 15% of the mean of the 4 human assessments for each plate with a CFU count above 30, and being within +/- 2 colonies from the mean human assessment for plates with a CFU count below 30. TNTC plates (either lawns or more than 300 CFU) have to be equivalent in the automatic assessment to the agreement between the human assessments.

We define false positives and negatives as over- or under-estimating the bacterial load on the plate. For example, if the reference count is 50, an automatic assessment of 43–58 is correct, while 59 and above is a false positive and 42 or lower is a false negative.

3.4.3 Precision of Automated Colony Counting

We assessed repeatability by re-imaging plates multiple times, with physical rotation and device changes between each measurement. Standard deviation was calculated for each sample; we report the coefficient of variation (CV, defined as the standard deviation divided by the mean count) for plates with more than 30 colonies and the absolute standard deviation for plates with fewer than 30 colonies.

4 Results

The full raw dataset of plate images and assessment data used to evaluate the platform can be made available upon reasonable request.

4.1 Equivalence Between Human Assessments on Images vs. Actual Plates

A quantification of equivalence was performed across the 35 plates mentioned in Section 2.2.1. Each plate was counted, and the absolute standard deviation was calculated. The average standard deviation across all 35 samples was 0.99 (less than one CFU difference on average). The average colony count on these plates was 27.5 CFU per plate.

4.2 Qualitative Review of Imaging Quality in Different Cases

(a) Trans-illumination

(b) Epi-illumination

Figure 2: Example of mold colonies on PDA. Note the color and morphological details visible under two illumination modes.

(a) Trans-illumination

(b) Epi-illumination

Figure 3: Another PDA plate highlighting similar growth patterns.

(a) Trans-illumination

(b) Epi-illumination

Figure 4: Heavily contaminated food sample on DRBC agar, showing the plate's purple hue and distinctive colony morphologies.

(a) Trans-illumination

(b) Epi-illumination

Figure 5: Less populated DRBC plate.

(a) Trans-illumination

(b) Epi-illumination

Figure 6: PCA plate inoculated with bacillus in high-fat cream cheese, resulting in a viscous surface layer.

(a) Trans-illumination

(b) Epi-illumination

Figure 7: Detailed view of the highly concentrated cream cheese inoculation, demonstrating how optical settings capture subtle structures.

Figure 8: Diluted, homogenized soil sample on PCA, revealing microbial colonies against a simpler background.

As demonstrated, the device has the ability to reproduce a wide range of microbiological plate types accurately in a digital format suitable for analysis.

4.2.1 Accuracy

A total of 242 plates were analyzed with 12,580 total colonies and an average of about 51 colonies per plate. These plates ranged broadly, including yeast and bacteria morphologies and molds on both pour and surface inoculation methods, as well as a wide range of artifacts (labels, barcodes, etc.). They also spanned both product and sample testing and environmental monitoring.

Figures 9–11 depict the correlation between automated model counts (x-axis) and four human reference counts (y-axis), with error bars representing the range. A 15% accuracy threshold (red cone) indicates acceptable vs. out-of-bounds assessments.

Figure 9: Correlation between manual and automatic results across the full range.

Figure 10: Correlation between manual and automatic results below 75 CFU per plate.

Figure 11: Correlation between manual and automatic results above 75 CFU per plate.

Figure 12: Bland-Altman plot indicating the agreement trend based on mean difference across various plate densities.

When applying the defined methodology in section 2.4.2, 219 out of 242 plates were correctly assessed, equivalent to 90.5%. The remaining 9.5% included 4 false positives (over-estimation of growth) and 19 false negatives (underestimation of growth).

Upon further analysis of the non-correct results, it is possible to document the cause of false results. In most cases (as seen in Figure 9), the outlier results also correlate with a large error bar which indicates the disagreement between human technicians. In these cases, even if the mean technician result deviates from the result from automated assessment, the accuracy for these cases between humans would also have been below the threshold.

4.2.2 Precision

We assessed 15 of the plates, each measured 12 times under different conditions (rotations, translations, and/or different devices). For plates under 30 CFU, the standard deviation was 0.44 CFU. For plates over 30 CFU, the average coefficient of variation (CV) was 5.88%.

4.2.3 Time Consumed

Technicians tracked, via stopwatch, the seconds needed to count each plate across various samples. At an average of 50 colonies per plate, this yielded a mean count time of 31s, or 0.63s per colony. This metric reflects only the time to perform the count, excluding documentation or cross-checking.

4.3 Discussion

As with any manual method, certain samples are more challenging than others. Given the established equivalence of the system’s outputs, verifying system performance is simpler than validating a completely new method. Standard proficiency testing (common to many quality control (QC) protocols) can be applied to the system, providing a straightforward benchmarking approach.

Everything (analysis pipelines, imaging device and firmware) is versioned, allowing qualification of each installed setup and comparison between older or newer pipeline generations. Because the existing dataset is large and varied, models can often handle sample types they have not previously encountered. If performance remains suboptimal, additional representative samples of the target species or morphology can be introduced to refine system performance.

Overall, we can conclude that machine learning models can replace human assessment for plate-based microbiological analysis.

- High accuracy: 90.5% of plates correctly assessed
- High precision: A low standard deviation of 0.44 CFU for low mean count plates and coefficient of variation of just 5.88% for higher count plates
- Productivity gains: A mean saving of 31 seconds per plate just for counting, not including documentation and other tasks, by utilizing an automated system

In doing this, a high degree of traceability and documentation is inherently generated. Once images (with appropriate metadata) are captured, they remain available for subsequent reviews or manual verification.